

STUDY OF FIELD TERMS IN WORLD TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract. *This article presents the opinions of a number of scientists in world linguistics on words and terminology in linguistics. Based on this, conclusions were drawn.*

Keywords: *linguistics, word, term, terminosystem, concept, concept.*

According to a number of scientists who studied the term in depth, terms are special words in the language. D.S. Lotte, S.A. Chaplugin, E.K. Dresen consider the term as a special word and combination and consider that they should have the following signs:

- 1) ambiguity of the term;
- 2) lack of synonyms;
- 3) harmony of main meanings (motivation);
- 4) systematicity;
- 5) brevity;
- 6) simplicity and comprehensibility;
- 7) accuracy;
- 8) implementation;
- 9) context independence;
- 10) not allowing to borrow words from foreign languages without reason (this term is "Own language") [1,15-16].

But another group of scientists puts forward the idea that any word can be a term. Based on this idea, scientists such as G.O. Vinokur, V.G. Gak, N.P. Kuzmin wrote several scientific works. According to G.O. Vinokur, "Any word can be a term ... terms are not special words, but only words that perform a special function" [2,5]. V. G. Gak expresses his opinion in this regard: "The lexicological and semantic analysis of terms, as well as the experience of general lexicography showed that the term is not a special type of lexical unit, but a type of use" [4,68]. N.P. Kuzmin admits that there is no difference between terms and special words: "Terms are a logical part of a special lexicon subjected to social processing and selection. No significant differences can be found between words and terms, other special and general vocabulary" [3,331]. The term and word relationship have always been the focus of researchers. "...terms are words and no linguistic phenomenon is alien to them" [5,124].

Based on the above opinion, if we consider that there is no significant difference between a term and a word, the theoretical understanding of the term in terminology narrows. In fact, any word can be a term, but it is necessary to specify the criteria according to which they are close to each other. For example, there are words that can exist in the language both as terms and as lexemes (a person's eyebrow is a saddle's eyebrow, a person's nose is a ship's nose, a shirt collar is a river collar). Focusing on these aspects of the issue helps to clarify the object of terminology.

We support the definition described by V. M. Leychik, who approached the linguistic nature of the term and its essence purely linguistically. According to him, the term is a complex and multi-layered unit. The lexical unit of the natural language on the basis of which the term is

formed forms its lower layer as the linguistic substrate of the term. Its upper layer is the logical superstratum, which represents the general laws of the formation of concepts and their definitions. Based on the description given by V. M. Leychik, if we conclude that the term contains the main features of a certain language lexical unit, it is reasonable to think about its having synonyms and polysemanticity.

A. Reformatsky believes that "the term is also a word with attention to the essence, only a special type of it" and suggests that the term be studied in the fields of "language" (lexical system of language) and "logic" (system of scientific knowledge) [6,46-54].

A. Superanskaya, without departing from the thoughts of V. Leychik and A. Reformatsky, writes in harmony with them: "One should always keep in mind the trinity that forms the basis of the term: knowledge of the subject, logical understanding and linguistic expression. In other words: only a third of the work belongs to the linguist in terminological activity, but it is very important" [7,17]. It can be seen that linguists are very interested in the characteristics of terms derived from lexical units, the process of formation of new nominative terminological units, as well as the process of forming terms as a result of the terminology of common literary language words.

In Uzbek linguistics, a number of serious scientific researches on terminology have been carried out. In these scientific studies, the concept of the term is defined, the main features are explained. For example, "Term (lat. terminus - limit, limit) - a word or phrase that expresses the concept of a special field of knowledge or activity. The term enters the common language through a certain terminological system, therefore, the term and common words are complementary lexical units" [8].

In Uzbek linguistics, in some cases, the term "term" and related terms are also used, and it is appropriate to distinguish them here. In Uzbek linguistics, certain studies have been carried out about terms, words and terminology. In the definition given to the special lexicon in the "Annotated Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" by A. Hojiyev, it is noted that the term also enters the special lexicon:

SPECIAL VOCABULARY. Words that name things and events related to different fields of work. Terminology and professional words are part of a special lexicon [9,166]. A linguist defines the term scientist as follows:

TERM is a word or phrase that clearly expresses the concept of something related to science, technology or other field, the scope of use of which is limited only to special fields. A. Hajiyev made serious comments about the wrongness of replacing the term with a coined term, its causes and consequences.

In the "Annotated Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" by N.Mahkamov, I.Ermatov, term and term, terminology and terminology are explained as the same concepts:

TERMS. Words used to express a specific meaning within a particular science or profession. There are two types of terms according to their usage: 1) scientific terms; 2) professional terms (q.) exact Terms.

TERMINOLOGY. A special branch of linguistics dealing with the principles of term formation and the problems of their regulation. exact Terminology.

TERMIN – (lat. terminus - a check, border, boundary mark). A word or phrase that clearly expresses the concept of something related to science, technology and other fields, the scope of use of which is limited to these fields; term Terms differ from common words in terms such as

being unambiguous, lacking in expressiveness and emotionality. For example, linguistic terms: sentence, possessive, noun, number, sound...; geometry terms: circle, triangle, rectangle...; physics terms: body, pressure, motion, field; chemical terms: water, silver, alkali, salts, etc. comparison Terms [10,112].

In Uzbek linguistics, U.Tursunov, S.Usmonov, A.Madvaliyev, H.Dadaboyev tried to explain the difference between terms, terms, and nomen in a series of works devoted to the analysis of terminology issues. For example, according to S.Usmanov's interpretation, a term is a word or phrase in a stable state that expresses a specific meaning even when it is taken outside the sentence [11,4]. A. Madvaliyev defined the acquisition of the term as the words and combinations used in science, science and technology fields or branches, and the term as the conditionally assigned names (nomenclature, nomen), in particular, geographical objects, place names (toponyms), and the use of Arabic islatih in the aspect of researches in the aspect of historical terminology, in relation to the concepts in the text of historical sources, is considered correct. H. Dadaboyev explains the difference between term and nomen as follows: one of the main differences between nomenclature and terminology is that nomen are usually not recorded in terminological dictionaries or take place in dictionaries in a very limited amount. It is known that the drug acetylsalicylic acid with the official scientific name is widely popular under the commercial name of aspirin and in the course of the development of various fields of science, some nouns can be transferred to the system of terms, from purely lexical nominative units to logical (logical) information, data elements, i.e. science terms" [12,10].

From the middle of the 20th century, attention to studying the field of terminology has increased in our country. A number of linguistic features of terms were studied in the researches of a number of scientists [13]. In recent years, the specific characteristics of terms have been studied in a new aspect in candidate and doctoral dissertations defended[14].

In linguistics, there is an increasing interest in studying terms in a comparative aspect. It is natural that the lexical study of the terms of two languages allows to determine the level of their presence in the text and to come to new scientific conclusions about defining mutually different aspects. In particular, O. Ahmedov on the topic "Linguistic analysis and translation problems of tax and customs terms in English and Uzbek" (2016), O.O. Bobokalonov on the topic "Linguocultural and linguocognitive features of the medicinal plant terminology in French and Uzbek" (2022) , M.K. Omonova defended their candidacy and doctoral theses on the topic "Lexical-semantic features of meliorative terms (in the case of English and Uzbek languages)" (2023).

In 2021, the creation of the "Explanatory Dictionary of Socio-Political Terms" created by a group of linguists was a major innovation in the field of terminology. This dictionary, which includes 4400 terms and combinations of terms actively used in the Uzbek language, includes new lexical units that appeared as a result of progress and changes in socio-political terminology.

Various features of new terms created due to the needs of the society are manifested, term creativity is being formed. Due to this need, one should not forget that certain requirements must be followed when choosing and using the term. "However, in Uzbekization of borrowed terms, it is necessary to proceed from the principles of convenience and popularization, without leaving the box. But it is not always appropriate to Uzbekize one lexical unit in the form of a word combination. In the choice of terms, the pursuit of universals based on the requirements of science and technology integration and globalization is a requirement of national science and technology

development" [15,122]. In this regard, N. Mahmudov expressed the following opinion: "Foreign words expressing concepts related to modern advanced science and technology, especially English (American version) words, are entering many languages. Even in today's Japanese, which is very wary of the influence of other languages, ninety-nine percent of the computer terminology is borrowed from English" [16,8]. Regarding the impact of the changes taking place in the Uzbek language on terms, M. Abdiyev expresses the following opinion: "Actually, the use of words in the language is free, the people cannot accept compulsion. Words that cannot be absorbed slowly fall out of circulation. Since changes in society are primarily reflected in language, there is a need to express them in language. If an alternative is not found, if it is not taken care of, that is, if it is not controlled, misunderstandings and mistakes may occur in understanding the meaning of the term" [17,6].

In the terminological system of the Uzbek language, there is a need to learn new terms that have arisen as a result of scientific and technical progress. As the language and society are under the influence of time, changes in space and time make terminology an object of constant research. This shows that it is an urgent task to scientifically study the terms used in the work of a certain writer. Because the entry of the terms into the artistic text, which arose due to the specialization of the concepts in the field of science, will allow to discover new aspects of the terminological unit, to come to reasonable scientific conclusions about the scope of application. In the next part of the study, the need to use the term in works related to artistic style is discussed.

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